

GLOBALIZATION AS A CATALYST FOR INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS: EVALUATING NEPAL'S GAINS AND LOSSES IN SAFTA, BIMSTEC, AND WTO

Shiv Prasad Sharma
MBA 5th Batch
Nepal Open University

Abstract:

This study explores whether globalization still drives international business amid rising protectionism, focusing on Nepal's engagement with SAFTA, BIMSTEC, and the WTO. While these agreements offer market access and trade benefits, Nepal struggles with infrastructure gaps, non-tariff barriers, and weak competitiveness. Recent U.S. tariff hikes and geopolitical tensions further challenge globalization, pushing nations toward regional trade blocs. The findings suggest Nepal must improve infrastructure, diversify exports, and strengthen trade policies to fully benefit from global and regional trade frameworks. This study uses existing theories, literature and data to analyze how globalization and trade agreements affect Nepal's economy through qualitative research methods.

Keywords: *Globalization, Regionalism, International Business, SAFTA, BIMSTEC, WTO, Trade, Tariff*

1. Introduction

1.1. Background of Globalization and Its Role in International Business

Globalization is the ongoing process of increasing interconnectedness between cross-boundary actors, driven by flows of people, ideas, goods, and capital. Globalization characterized by the increased interconnectedness of national economies through trade, investment, and technology, has long been seen as a driving force behind the expansion of international business (Bhagwati, 2004).

Globalization has fundamentally transformed international business by accelerating cross-border trade, investment flows, and technological integration (Gereffi & Fernandez-Stark, 2016). Since the late 20th century, the liberalization of trade policies, advancements in digital communication, and the expansion of multinational corporations (MNCs) have deepened economic interdependence among nations (Dicken, 2015). The establishment of global institutions like the World Trade Organization (WTO) and regional trade blocs such as the South Asian Free Trade Area (SAFTA) and the Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-

Sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation (BIMSTEC) has further facilitated economic integration by reducing tariffs and standardizing trade regulations (WTO, 2023).

However, recent geopolitical shifts towards the rising protectionism, the US-China trade war, Brexit, and supply chain disruptions from the COVID-19 pandemic etc have sparked debates about the sustainability of globalization (Rodrik, 2018). Some argue that globalization is stagnating, with nations increasingly favoring regionalism or economic nationalism (Baldwin, 2016).

In this evolving global landscape as a developing nation Nepal has actively engaged in both regional initiatives like the South Asian Free Trade Area (SAFTA) and the Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-Sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation (BIMSTEC), as well as the global framework of the World Trade Organization (WTO), with the expectation of leveraging these platforms to enhance its international business and achieve economic development (Pandey et al., 2022). Despite participating in multiple trade agreements, have struggled to harness the benefits of globalization, raising concerns about structural inefficiencies, policy gaps, and asymmetrical power dynamics in international trade (WTO, 2023).

This essay critically examines whether globalization continues to act as a catalyst for enhancing international business, particularly focusing on Nepal's engagement with SAFTA, BIMSTEC, and WTO. By reviewing the literature and analyzing official statistics, the paper will explore Nepal's current trade performance within these frameworks, assess the barriers it faces, and evaluate the extent to which these international agreements have contributed to Nepal's economic growth.

1.2. Objectives of the Study

This research aims to reach:

- a) Evaluate the continued relevance of globalization in shaping international business amid contemporary geopolitical challenges.
- b) Assess Nepal's participation in SAFTA, BIMSTEC, and WTO, analyzing its trade performance and integration levels.
- c) Identify key barriers preventing Nepal from maximizing gains from these trade agreements.
- d) Propose policy recommendations to enhance Nepal's trade competitiveness and benefits from globalization.

1.3. Research Questions

- a) Is globalization still a significant driver of international business in the current geopolitical climate marked by protectionism and regionalism?
- b) Why has Nepal failed to fully capitalize on SAFTA, BIMSTEC, and WTO, despite decades of membership?

2. Theoretical Framework: Globalization and Regionalism in International

2.1. Theories of Globalization:

Several theoretical perspectives attempt to explain the phenomenon of globalization and its implications for international business. Economic liberalization is the main perspectives that often rooted in neoliberal ideology, posits that the reduction of state intervention in the economy, including deregulation, privatization, and the liberalization of trade and capital flows, fosters economic growth and efficiency on a global scale (Friedman, 1962; Hayek, 1944). This perspective suggests that the removal of barriers to international trade and investment allows businesses to operate more freely across borders, leading to increased competition, innovation, and ultimately, greater global prosperity.

The theory of comparative advantage, first articulated by David Ricardo (1817), provides a foundational economic rationale for international trade. This theory argues that countries should specialize in producing goods and services in which they have a relative cost advantage and trade with other nations for goods and services they produce less efficiently. Globalization, by facilitating cross-border trade, allows countries to exploit their comparative advantages, leading to increased global output and consumption. Businesses operating internationally can leverage these national specializations to optimize their production processes and access a wider range of inputs and markets.

Institutional theory emphasizes the role of formal and informal rules, norms, and organizations in shaping economic behavior and international business activities (North, 1990; Scott, 2008). In the context of globalization, international institutions such as the World Trade Organization (WTO) play a crucial role in establishing and enforcing the rules of global trade, reducing uncertainty and facilitating cross-border transactions (Jackson, 1997). Similarly, regional trade agreements (RTAs) create specific institutional frameworks that govern trade and investment among member countries, influencing the strategies and operations of businesses within those regions (Aggarwal & Urata, 2006). These institutional

structures can both enable and constrain international business activities, highlighting the importance of understanding the regulatory and normative environment.

2.2. Role of Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs):

Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs) represent a significant trend in international economic relations, with numerous agreements established across the globe. The benefits of RTAs are often cited as including enhanced market access for member countries through the reduction or elimination of tariffs and other trade barriers among themselves (Frankel, 1997). This preferential access can lead to increased trade flows and economic integration within the region. Furthermore, RTAs can facilitate deeper economic integration through the harmonization of standards, regulations, and investment policies, potentially attracting more foreign direct investment and fostering regional value chains (Baldwin, 2006).

Despite these potential benefits, RTAs also present challenges. One significant concern is the potential for asymmetrical gains, where some member countries benefit more than others due to differences in economic size, competitiveness, and the structure of their economies (Hoekman & Schiff, 2001). Developing countries, in particular, may face difficulties in competing with more industrialized partners within a regional bloc. Moreover, while RTAs aim to reduce tariffs, non-tariff barriers (NTBs) such as differing product standards, customs procedures, and sanitary and phytosanitary regulations can still impede trade among member countries (Evenett & Hoekman, 2006). Overcoming these NTBs often requires significant policy coordination and institutional capacity building within the region.

2.3. Globalization vs. Regionalism Debate:

The relationship between globalization and regionalism has been a subject of ongoing debate among scholars and policymakers. Proponents of globalization argue that it fosters greater trade expansion through the reduction of barriers on a multilateral basis, encourages foreign direct investment (FDI) flows, facilitates the transfer of technology and knowledge across borders, and promotes greater competition, leading to lower prices and higher quality goods and services (Bhagwati, 2004; Wolf, 2004). They contend that a globally integrated economy maximizes efficiency and promotes overall economic welfare.

However, there are significant critiques over globalization. The rise of protectionist sentiments and trade wars in recent years, often fueled by concerns about job losses in developed countries and unfair trade practices, challenges the notion of an ever-increasingly

open global economy (Rodrik, 2018; Stiglitz, 2002). Critics also point to the potential for globalization to exacerbate income inequality both within and between countries, as well as its potential negative impacts on the environment and labor standards in some developing economies (Wade, 2004).

3. Methodology

This research employs a qualitative research design to analyze the role of globalization in international business, with a specific focus on Nepal's engagement with SAFTA, BIMSTEC, and the WTO. The methodology is structured around secondary data analysis and an extensive literature review, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of Nepal's trade dynamics within these frameworks.

3.1. Research Design

This study adopts an exploratory and analytical approach, examining existing theories, policies, and empirical data to assess Nepal's trade performance and challenges. The qualitative methodology is chosen because:

- It allows for an in-depth examination of complex trade dynamics.
- It facilitates the interpretation of policy impacts and institutional constraints.
- It helps identify patterns and trends in Nepal's trade performance through historical and contemporary data.

3.2. Data Collection Methods

The research relies on secondary data from Government and Institutional Reports, Nepal Rastra Bank (NRB) Annual Reports, Ministry of Industry, Commerce, and Supplies (MoICS) reports, World Trade Organization (WTO) trade policy reviews, South Asian Watch on Trade, Economics and Environment (SAWTEE) studies, Asian Development Bank (ADB) and World Bank reports on regional trade. Data and secondary information from academic literature, Peer-reviewed journal articles on globalization, regionalism, and trade agreements, books and working papers on international trade theories is absorbed. The data and information also retrieves from Trade Agreements and Policy Documents like SAFTA and BIMSTEC agreements, Nepal's WTO accession documents and commitments, Global Trade

Databases & News Reports, UNCTAD, UNIDO, and Global Trade Alert reports, News articles on U.S. tariff policies and their impact on Nepal.

3.3. Data Analysis Techniques

The study employs qualitative content analysis to assess Nepal's trade trends, policy effectiveness, and institutional constraints. Comparative analysis evaluates Nepal's performance against regional peers and global protectionism's impact, using trade statistics and policy documents.

3.4. Limitations of the study

The key limitations of the study are followings:

- The study relies exclusively on secondary data, which limits its ability to capture current on-the-ground realities and stakeholder perspectives that primary research could provide.
- The rapidly evolving global trade environment, particularly recent U.S. protectionist policies, may affect the continued relevance of some findings over time.
- Gaps in sector-specific trade data constrain the analysis of Nepal's export performance across different industries and product categories.
- The research focuses only on multilateral frameworks (SAFTA, BIMSTEC, WTO) without considering important bilateral trade relationships that influence Nepal's commerce.
- The qualitative methodology, while appropriate for policy analysis, cannot provide statistically validated conclusions about trade patterns and economic impacts.

3.5. Ethical Considerations.

This study used only public data with proper citations. No confidential information was collected. All sources are credited to avoid plagiarism. The research maintains objectivity without bias in analyzing Nepal's trade situation.

4. Analysis of Globalization and Regionalism in the Current Context

4.1. The Evolving Landscape of Globalization:

Many people believe globalization is growing, but some experts now think it might be slowing down or even reversing. This idea is called "slowbalization" or "deglobalization."

The first thing is that, trade wars between big economies have led to higher taxes on imports and more uncertainty, hurting global trade (Evenett & Fritz, 2023). Second, the COVID-19 pandemic showed how risky long supply chains can be. Now, many companies and governments want to make production more local or regional to avoid future problems (Baldwin & Freeman, 2020).

New technology, like automation and 3D printing, also lets companies make goods closer to home instead of relying on foreign suppliers. At the same time, nationalism and protectionism are growing; making countries less open to free global trade. As a result, global supply chains are changing. They may become shorter and more regional, which will affect how businesses operate worldwide. Finally, digital technology is making it easier to trade services and data across borders. But it could also reduce the need for shipping physical goods and create new digital trade barriers.

4.2. The Shifting Dynamics of Regionalism:

Regional trade agreements (RTAs) are changing in today's world. These agreements still help member countries by giving them special trade benefits and lower taxes on imports. However, it's becoming harder for these deals to create strong economic bonds between countries. This is because different nations have competing interests, and global power struggles make cooperation difficult (Katzenstein, 2005). Political conflicts between countries can weaken regional groups and slow down their progress.

Nationalism is growing in many places, making countries less willing to open their markets further. Also, if the world splits into competing trade blocs, it could create new trade barriers between regions. But RTAs also have advantages. In an unstable global economy, they can provide stability and stronger ties between friendly nations. New types of regional partnerships are also forming. These focus not just on trade but also on supply chains, digital trade, and climate change. Businesses, local governments, and other groups are now often involved, not just national leaders (Mansfield & Milner, 1999).

4.3. Interplay between Globalization and Regionalism:

The link between globalization and regional trade deals is more complicated now than before. In the past, some saw regional agreements as steps toward global free trade, but today the situation is different (Baldwin, 2016). Now that globalization is slowing, countries may focus more on regional partnerships instead of worldwide trade. This could help them deal with

global uncertainty. But it also risks dividing the world economy into competing trade blocs, making trade between regions harder and more expensive (Bhagwati, 2008).

Developing countries face both risks and opportunities in global trade. While regional agreements provide market access and supply chain integration, they may also trap nations in weaker trade blocs. Countries must strategically balance regional and global trade approaches to maximize benefits (World Bank, 2023). As globalization slows, regional deals offer stability but risk fragmenting the world economy. Success depends on carefully combining regional partnerships with global engagement to ensure sustainable growth while avoiding trade isolation. Wise management of this balance will determine future trade outcomes.

5. Nepal's International Business Experience with SAFTA, BIMSTEC, and WTO

Nepal is a landlocked developing country, participates in international trade through agreements like SAFTA, BIMSTEC, and WTO to boost its economy. While these agreements provide opportunities, Nepal faces major challenges in global business. The country mainly exports textiles, carpets and agricultural products, with India being its biggest trade partner. However, poor infrastructure, growing trade deficits, and weak competitiveness create problems. Nepal's heavy dependence on Indian markets and increasing business deficits in international trade show the need for better policies and supply chains to improve its global trade performance (Pandey et al., 2022).

Table no. 1

International Business of Nepal (in Nrs. million)

Fiscal Year	Import	Export	Deficit	Deficit Value (Times more)
2077/78	153983.7	14112.4	-139871.3	9.17
2078/79	192044.8	20003.1	-172041.7	10.41
2079/80	161173.2	15714.1	-145459.1	9.75
2080/81	159298.6	15238.1	-144060.5	9.57

Source: Nepal Rastra Bank, Annual Reports

This is the international trade data from fiscal years 2077/78 to 2080/81. During these four years, Nepal imported much more than it exported. It's about 9 to 11 times more in value. The trade deficit peaked in 2078/79 at -172,041.7 million, driven by the highest import level of 192,044.8 million, while exports remained minimal at just 20,003.1 million. Although the deficit slightly improved in 2080/81 to -144,060.5 million, this was primarily due to a reduction in imports rather than growth in exports, which stayed alarmingly low at 15,238.1

million. The data underscores Nepal's chronic trade imbalance, indicating a struggling export sector and excessive dependence on foreign goods.

Nepal's imports mostly come from India and China. Over four years (2077/78-2080/81), India supplied the most between 62-64% of total imports, peaking at 120,015 million NPR in 2078/79. China was second, providing 14-19%, with imports rising to 29,878 million by 2080/81.

Figure-1

Trade Import and its distribution (in Nrs. million)

Source: Nepal Rastra Bank, Annual Reports

Other countries' share dropped from 24% to 19% in the same period. This shows Nepal relies heavily on India, with China slowly increasing its share. Depending too much on just two countries is risky. Nepal should diversify imports to avoid trade problems and ensure stable supply.

Table-2

Trade Export and its distribution (in Nrs. million)

Fiscal Year	India	China	Other Country
2077/78	10637.2	101.6	3373.6
2078/79	15522.02	80.9	4400
2079/80	10668.6	176.6	4868.9
2080/81	10317.7	258.9	4661.5

Source: Nepal Rastra Bank, Annual Reports

Nepal's export data shows most goods go to India, which buys about 68-78% of everything Nepal sells abroad. In 2078/79, exports to India were highest at 15,522 million rupees, but dropped to 10,318 million by 2080/81. Very little goes to China (less than 2%), though it increased from 102 million to 259 million over four years. Other countries buy about 22-31% of Nepal's exports, growing slowly from 3,374 million to 4,662 million rupees. The numbers prove Nepal depends too much on India for exports while business with China remains very small. Other countries are buying from Nepal but the amounts are still low and there lies a great gap and opportunity of expansion.

5.1. South Asian Free Trade Area (SAFTA)

SAFTA was established in 2006 with aim to foster trade liberalization among the eight SAARC member states. Nepal, as a signatory, anticipated significant benefits from reduced tariffs and enhanced regional economic cooperation within a market of over 2.08 billion people. The agreement's core objective is to minimize trade barriers, thereby promoting intra-regional commerce and integration. Nepal specifically hoped that SAFTA would broaden its business opportunities within South Asia and provide access to larger markets for its products.

5.1.1. Nepal's Gains in SAFTA

I. Market Expansion: SAFTA broadened Nepal's market access in South Asia. It gives benefit for export sectors like textiles, carpets, tea, and agro-products, allowing businesses to tap into neighboring countries' demand.

II. Duty-Free Access: Nepal's competitiveness is increased in the wide range of market of SAARC nation mainly in India and Bangladesh by its preferential and duty-free access. Nepal is also getting LCD benefit.

III. Boost to SMEs and Employment: Trade liberalization under SAFTA has supported Nepal's SMEs growth. This was crucial for local employment and entrepreneurship enabling their growth and economic contribution.

IV. Trade Diversification: SAFTA encouraged Nepal to explore markets beyond India, increasing trade with other countries like Bangladesh and Sri Lanka. This will support to reduce reliance on a single market and enhancing trade resilience.

V. Policy Reforms and Harmonization: Aligning with SAFTA requirements, Nepal undertook trade policy reforms and harmonization. These will improve compliance and enhance its trade regime's competitiveness.

5.1.2. Challenges for Nepal in SAFTA

I. Non-Tariff Barriers (NTBs): Even with lower tariffs under SAFTA, Nepalese exporters still face many Non-Tariff Barriers in member countries like India and Bangladesh. That includes complicated paperwork, customs delays, and strict technical rules that make it hard for goods to move easily.

II. Trade Deficit and Dependency: Nepal has a big and ongoing trade deficit mostly with India. We imports much more from India than our exports. There is a question rising about SAFTA that is whether the benefits are fully in the favour of Nepal or not?

III. Poor Infrastructure: Bad infrastructure such as poor transportation, limited electricity, and inefficient logistics increases the production costs for Nepalese businesses. This limits their ability to compete in the SAFTA region.

IV. Weak Institutional Capacity: Nepal does not have strong enough institutions to negotiate properly and enforce its trade rights and duties under SAFTA. This weakness limits our ability to take full advantage of the agreement.

V. Underutilization of Trade Preferences: Due to low awareness, complex rules about where goods come from, and poor paperwork many Nepalese businesses don't know about the trade benefits under SAFTA. So, there is the question always raised regarding the utilization of trade opportunity.

5.1.3. Recommendations for Nepal within SAFTA

I. Address NTBs through Dialogue: Nepal should talk more with other SAFTA countries to reduce Non-Tariff Barriers and make trade rules more similar for easier trade.

II. Invest in Infrastructure: The government needs to spend more on better transport, storage, and energy supply. This will lower trade costs and make Nepalese exports more competitive in international market.

III. Strengthen Trade Institutions: Nepal needs to make its government trade agencies stronger so it can better use SAFTA benefits and protect its trade interests.

IV. Promote Export Diversification: Nepal should focus on exporting more valuable goods and services like herbs, tourism, and processed foods to make its trade stronger.

V. Reform Trade Policies: Nepal needs clear trade policies and training for small businesses so they can better understand and use SAFTA rules to help the economy.

5.2. Nepal and the Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-Sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation (BIMSTEC)

BIMSTEC, established in 1997, connects South Asia and Southeast Asia, comprising Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Myanmar, Nepal, Sri Lanka, and Thailand. Its objectives include fostering cooperation in trade, transportation, energy, technology, and tourism to promote economic growth and improve livelihoods in the Bay of Bengal region. Nepal joined BIMSTEC in 2004, viewing it as a vital alternative to the often-stagnant SAARC, offering new avenues for regional engagement.

5.2.1. Nepal's Gains in BIMSTEC I. Diversification of Trade Routes: BIMSTEC can give Nepal other trade routes through Bangladesh and Myanmar. It will reduce our reliance on Indian ports and will improve access to the Bay of Bengal for better trade connections.

II. Energy Cooperation: The BIMSTEC Grid project could allow Nepal to sell its extra hydropower to countries that need energy in south-east Asian region. This will make earning money and helping the region's energy security.

III. Infrastructure Development: The BIMSTEC transport plan aims to improve roads, railways, and ports in the region. If this success then this will greatly help Nepal's trade and transit by reducing logistical problems.

IV. Access to New Markets: The planned BIMSTEC Free Trade Agreement could give Nepal chances to sell its goods to south-east Asian countries. It will help our economy grow in new areas beyond South Asia.

V. Strategic Regional Engagement: Because of the SAARC challenges, BIMSTEC is becoming a more important way for Nepal to work with other countries in the region and pursue development with a wider group.

5.2.2. Challenges for Nepal in BIMSTEC

I. Political Instability: Nepal's changing politics have often stopped us from actively participating in BIMSTEC activities. This affects our leadership and involvement in regional projects.

II. Limited Institutional Capacity: BIMSTEC's secretariat has limited power and resources which has slowed down the implementation of projects and agreements. This is affecting Nepal's ability to benefit fully.

III. Geopolitical Tensions: Strained relationships between some BIMSTEC countries, like India and Nepal, India and Bangladesh, Bangladesh and Myanmar at times can hurt the unity and progress of BIMSTEC projects.

IV. Underutilization of Agreements: Even with transit deals with Bangladesh through BIMSTEC, Nepal hasn't fully used Bangladeshi ports because of ongoing logistical and diplomatic problems. So the utilization of the agreement properly for the national benefit is also the matter of concern.

V. Lack of a Formal Charter: There is lack of clear BIMSTEC legal charter. This has caused confusion about its long-term goals and operations that hinder the member states to work together effectively.

5.2.3. Recommendations for Nepal within BIMSTEC

I. Enhance Political Commitment: There is a saying that 'nothing will be good if politics gone wrong'. Nepal needs stable politics and a strong commitment to BIMSTEC to have more influence in the regional group.

II. Strengthen Institutional Frameworks: Nepal should push for a stronger BIMSTEC Secretariat with more resources for better coordination and project implementation. This will give power to us for the best business climate.

III. Leverage Energy Exports: Nepal should actively join BIMSTEC energy projects to benefit from its hydropower, earning money and helping regional energy security.

IV. Utilize Alternative Trade Routes: Nepal has limited trade route so it limits the ability of business. So, Nepal should work to fully use transit deals with Bangladesh to access seaports and diversify our trade routes.

V. Advocate for a BIMSTEC Charter: Nepal should strongly support a formal charter for BIMSTEC to clarify its goals and improve cooperation among members. Political delays, resource constraints, and overlapping commitments with SAFTA dilute BIMSTEC's effectiveness

5.3. World Trade Organization and Nepal

Nepal became the 147th member of the WTO in April 2004. We are the first LDC to complete the full accession process. Membership was sought to integrate Nepal's economy into the global market, attract foreign investment, and boost exports. WTO membership also needed to reforms in Nepal's trade policies to align with international standards.

5.3.1. Nepal's Gains in the WTO

I. Enhanced Market Access: WTO membership gave Nepal equal access to global markets. It is helping us export goods and services to more countries worldwide.

II. Legal Protection and Dispute Settlement: Nepal can use the WTO's system to solve trade disagreements with other members and ensure everyone follows trade rules. This will give wings like us that with weak negotiation and diplomatic power.

III. Trade Policy Reforms: Joining the WTO made Nepal change its trade rules like lowering tariffs and simplifying procedures to match international standards.

IV. Technical Assistance and Capacity Building: As a poor country in the WTO, Nepal has received many kinds of technical assistance and capacity enhancement. It will help to build its trade skills and participate better in global trade.

V. Investment Promotion: Being a WTO member has made Nepal's trade and investment environment more stable and clear. This may create the space and possibility to attract foreign investment.

5.3.2. Challenges Faced by Nepal in the WTO

I. Trade Deficit: Despite better market access from the WTO, Nepal's imports are much higher than its exports. This raises the concerns about our global competitiveness. To overcome and replace the import with sufficient internal production is the main challenge.

II. Limited Export Diversification: Nepal exports only a few types of products to a small number of markets. This makes us vulnerable to economic problems and limits its ability to benefit from the WTO.

III. Compliance with WTO Agreements: It's hard for Nepal to follow WTO rules, especially those about intellectual property and health standards because we have limited resources and skills.

IV. SME Competitiveness: Small businesses in Nepal often lack the money, technology, and market knowledge to compete well in the international markets opened by the WTO. So, SME's are dying due to the big multinational companies.

V. Infrastructure Constraints: Poor transportation, logistics, and communication systems are the weak infrastructures that hinder the Nepalese business environment. This makes Nepal's trade less efficient and harder to meet international market needs.

5.3.3. Recommendations for Nepal within the WTO

I. Export Diversification Strategies: Nepal needs clear plans to export a wider variety of products to different markets. This will make it less dependent on the limited number of products. If the production variety increases, our business will be more stable economically. Export business is very small in volume with China, so Nepal must think international business to sell in China. As China is the large producer in the world, competing with the production may be challenging, but we can alternatively choose to attract a large number of Chinese as tourists.

II. Capacity Building for Compliance: Nepal must enhance the capacity for the utilization of WTO agreement. We invest in making our institutions stronger to follow WTO rules and fully benefit from its membership. Nepal government should increase consultative services to enhance the capacity of Nepalese enterprise for the quality service and products.

III. Support for SMEs: The government should help Nepalese small businesses with money, training, and market information to make them more competitive globally. Local SME's sustaining strategies should make and follow.

IV. Infrastructure Development: Nepal should prioritize investments in infrastructure developments like transportation, logistics, and customs to improve trade efficiency and lower costs. Nepal must priorities its infrastucture development relating to business expansion.

V. Active Participation in WTO Negotiations: Nepal needs active participate in WTO talks. Our negotiation power and commercial diplomatic strength and relationship should expand. Nepal should raise voice to represent the interests of poor countries and ensure its development needs.

5.4. Nepal's Limited Gains from Regional and Global Trade Frameworks

Nepal is landlocked least developed country. There is a great struggle to fully capitalize on the opportunities presented by evolving globalization and the rise of regionalism, specifically within the South Asian Free Trade Area (SAFTA), the Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-Sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation (BIMSTEC), and the World Trade Organization (WTO). Despite membership, Nepal's trade performance remains weak, characterized by a persistent trade deficit (Nepal Rastra Bank, 2024). This report analyzes the key constraints hindering Nepal's ability to benefit from these frameworks.

One significant impediment is Nepal's supply-side limitations. A narrow production base, coupled with low productivity and inadequate infrastructure (e.g., transportation, energy), restricts Nepal's capacity to produce goods and services that meet the quality and quantity demands of regional and global markets (MoICS, 2023). For instance, while traditional handicrafts hold export potential, inconsistent quality and limited scale hinder their competitiveness.

Furthermore, non-tariff barriers (NTBs) and para-tariff barriers within SAFTA continue to impede Nepali exports. Complex customs procedures, sanitary and phytosanitary regulations, and transit issues, particularly through India, increase trade costs and reduce competitiveness (SAWTEE, 2022). Nepal's heavy trade dependence on India further complicates the benefits from SAFTA. While tariffs have been reduced, the vast economic disparity often overshadows potential gains for Nepal (World Bank, 2023). In Fiscal Year 2022/23, India accounted for approximately 65% of Nepal's total trade (Nepal Rastra Bank, 2024).

Within BIMSTEC, Nepal's gains are limited by the framework's broad focus beyond trade, coupled with significant connectivity challenges as a landlocked nation. Poor infrastructure and high transit costs hinder trade with other member states, particularly those in Southeast Asia (Asian Development Bank, 2021).

Despite access to the global market through the WTO, Nepal's lack of a competitive exportable surplus restricts its ability to leverage this membership. Supply-side constraints and quality issues prevent Nepali products from effectively competing internationally (UNCTAD, 2022). Moreover, Nepal's low negotiating capacity as a small economy can limit its ability to advocate for its specific needs within the WTO framework.

The changing landscape of globalization, with evolving global value chains and increased competition, necessitates a robust domestic capacity that Nepal currently lacks. While regionalism offers proximity advantages, Nepal's internal weaknesses prevent it from fully exploiting these opportunities. Addressing these fundamental structural constraints, enhancing export competitiveness, improving trade facilitation, and strategically engaging in these platforms are crucial for Nepal to realize the potential benefits of regional and global trade frameworks.

5.5. The Current Tariff War and Its Impact on Globalization, Regionalism, and Nepal

According to Tax Foundation (2025), since US President Donald Trump's re-election, has escalated tariffs, imposing a 10% baseline rate on all imports and up to 145% on China, citing trade deficits and national security under the International Emergency Economic Powers Act (IEEPA). These measures aim to reshore manufacturing but have triggered retaliatory tariffs from China (84%-145%), the EU (25%), and others, disrupting global trade. The U.S. weighted average tariff rate is now 27.8%, the highest since 1943, potentially reducing U.S. GDP by 1% and household incomes by 1.3%.

While globalization has slowed due to supply chain vulnerabilities, data shows no robust shift toward regional trade dominance. However, regional blocs like the EU, USMCA, and ASEAN are strengthening intra-regional trade, accounting for 54% of global commerce (UNIDO, 2025).

Trump's policies may reduce U.S. aid to Nepal, particularly in climate and reproductive health, while stricter migration policies could hinder Nepali workers. Nepal's economy, sandwiched between India and China, faces uncertainty as U.S.-China tensions escalate. India's potential trade benefits from U.S.-China tariffs could indirectly affect Nepal's trade dynamics (Global Voices, 2024).

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, globalization remains a powerful force in international business, but its benefits are unevenly distributed. Nepal's participation in SAFTA, BIMSTEC, and the WTO has provided some opportunities such as market access and regional cooperation. However, persistent challenges including poor infrastructure, non-tariff barriers, and a narrow export base have limited Nepal's gains. The rise of protectionism and shifting trade dynamics further complicate its ability to compete globally. Without significant reforms, Nepal risks falling further behind in the evolving trade landscape.

To harness globalization's potential, Nepal must prioritize infrastructure development, diversify its exports, and strengthen trade policies. Active engagement in regional and global trade negotiations is crucial to address asymmetries and secure favorable terms. Additionally, improving institutional capacity and supporting small businesses will enhance competitiveness. While geopolitical tensions and slowing globalization pose risks, strategic adaptation can help Nepal turn challenges into opportunities. The path forward requires bold policy actions and sustained commitment to ensure Nepal benefits from both regional and global trade frameworks in the long run.

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